

ISSUES OF DEVELOPMENT OF ENVIRONMENTAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS BASED ON INTEGRATED EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article analyzes the issues of developing environmental competence of students based on integrated education and describes the scientific and pedagogical foundations.

Key words: competence, ecological education, reproductive, alternative, retrospective, ecological competence, competence, pedagogical.

INTRODUCTION. Today, educational tools for developing environmental competence are interpreted only as a narrow pedagogical task. However, the problems of the current environmental situation require a broader, socio-philosophical approach to the issue. The tasks of environmentalization of the educational process should consist of the humanization of the educational complex, the interests of harmonizing the relationship between man and nature. For this reason, the formation of an integrative educational system in higher education, the formation of ecological knowledge and skills based on interdisciplinary cooperation, and the issues of ecological education and upbringing in Uzbekistan are gaining relevance. The growing global environmental crisis, environmental pollution and other problems require the eco-movement to become an active force.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Pedagogical aspects of the foundations of environmental education, the causes of environmental risks in the era of globalization, ways to eliminate them, scientific research aimed at developing some aspects of environmental competence in students Q. Abdurahimov, I. Kh. Ayubova, P. Berdanova, N. Bozorova, R. Kh. Djurayev, Y. Ahmadaliyev, N. Isakulova, Sh. Kamolkho'jayev, A. Malikova, M. E. Musayeva, V. Nikitin, N. O'. Nishonova, H. Norbo'tayev, T. Sapparov, V. N. Sattorov, H. Togayev, E. O. It was carried out by Turdikulov, U. Turdikulov, D. Tokhliyev, A.S. Tokhtayev, A. Ergashev, Sh. Yunusova.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. In the development of environmental competence among students, the issue of combining natural sciences and social and humanitarian sciences on the basis of integrated education is important. It shows two relatively independent processes. First, the possibility of a complex and systematic approach to environmental education arises from the need to harmonize different areas of education, to connect alternative directions based on a single goal. In the second direction, it is necessary to maintain the historical and logical consistency of connections between different forms and levels of ecological education, and to ensure connections between their means and methods. In other words, the common character of these directions is manifested in their relationship to each other. In addition, on the basis of connecting education and upbringing with the interests of nature protection, a general commonality emerges, and its features become a necessary condition for the development of environmental moral responsibility.

The reconstruction of the higher education system based on ecological needs has moved universal values, including environmental education, to the center of pedagogical policy and ideology. The effective solution of this task requires the generalization of all fields of education based on scientific methodological principles. In fact, it is in the process of environmental education that there are opportunities to eliminate the gaps and conflicts of different forms of science and social consciousness in the fields of education. Therefore, education in the field of nature protection should be an integral part of the training of qualified personnel at any level of educational complex, rather than being an event artificially and mechanistically added to general education. Its content may change depending on the social, economic, political conditions, and ecological situation in different countries.

Nowadays, the tasks of higher pedagogic education and training - ensuring the integration of various forms of social consciousness with ecological thinking - have become more urgent than ever. The level and content of environmentalization of certain forms of social consciousness, as well as the effectiveness of practical activities of nature protection are becoming a unique criterion of historical development. Therefore, based on the current opportunities, it is important to provide scientific-methodological connections of various subjects in the education of students' ecological worldview.

In general, the levels and directions of the environmental education and training process, based on the interests of increasing the responsibility for nature protection, are dependent on solving the following methodological tasks:

a) elimination of contradictions in special concepts, terms, definitions related to environmental education, while maintaining historical and logical consistency, succession relations;

b) identification of global, regional, national and local environmental problems of various environmental education and training areas and coordination of means and methods of solving them on the basis of common interests;

c) consists of coordinating alternative environmental activities in the fields of education and training, increasing their effectiveness and optimizing them. For this, from the initial stages, social institutions of education and training should strictly define their conceptual work programs and the tasks of environmental activities. Also, in order to ensure the continuity of the ecological education-education process in each direction, based on the principle of going from simple to complex, drawing up plans with defined perspectives, can give results only by relying on scientific and philosophical methodology.

Scientific generalization and systematization determine the effectiveness of environmental education by identifying the causes, consequences, development prospects of the society, the objective and subjective factors that drive them, and their laws. It is necessary to introduce a set of knowledge related to ecological competence, concepts of new content into the minds of students, to determine the possibilities of historical, logical connection with their previously acquired theoretical knowledge. It is practically very difficult to educate students to become active fighters of nature protection, responsible persons who meet the environmental requirements of the present time by using only the method of instruction or strict administrative and legal measures [1].

In order to educate the growing young generation as a person who understands ecological needs and deeply feels the responsibility of nature protection, first of all, it is necessary to explain to him the connection with the environment in which he lives. However,

people have not yet determined their relationship to the concept of "whose" and "for whom" natural resources. In fact, declaring that forests, rivers, lakes, land and other natural resources belong to the people represents a kind of vague generality, dispossession. As long as we are not able to educate students about the concrete concepts of "nation's", "ours", "mine", "our generations" in relation to natural resources, statements about the ecological and moral position will remain slogans. Therefore, it is necessary to form social ecological responsibility, to inculcate that the preservation of nature and the environment is the social duty of "everyone".

The level of development of the method of education of ecological competence in students is reflected in the connection of theoretical knowledge about the balance of the biosphere with the tasks of nature protection. It should also be noted that it is not easy to form the ecological qualities of a student who has a sufficient level of knowledge about nature protection. For this purpose, the complex of ecological knowledge is connected with the ecological interests of the society and becomes its vital needs, it can give the expected results. For example, a student understands the need to protect nature, but the reason for his non-compliance and indifference in his daily activities goes back to the fact that ecological knowledge has not become a belief and moral norm [2].

In the requirements, it is appropriate to distinguish two interrelated tasks of education in the development of environmental competence. The first is the formation of scientific ecological thinking and worldview based on the spiritual and historical values of nature protection. The second is to improve the practical possibilities, methods and means of applying environmental responsibility to social life. The combination of these two areas based on common interests plays a major role in the creation of an ecologically active attitude to nature.

The development of environmental competence in students is not a social phenomenon that occurs spontaneously, spontaneously, automatically, but requires the proper functioning of educational mechanisms at various levels. In this case, objective conditions create an opportunity for the formation of environmental responsibility, and subjective factors make them a reality. The successful solution of this problem is not to carry out economic or administrative activities under the banner of seasonality, but to preserve the relations of succession in the historical ecological heritage of the general public and to continuously develop them, is an educational and political task. In particular, it is a complex process of environmentalization of enlightenment, politics, law, science, ethics, art and other similar fields. One of the necessary conditions for the formation of ecological responsibility is to determine the objective and subjective reasons for the emergence of ecological consciousness and the mechanisms of their development, based on the scientific understanding of nature and human relations. In the case of global environmental crisis, the need to introduce innovative approaches to environmental education in countries increases. Therefore, in Uzbekistan, improving the process of environmental education and upbringing on an innovative basis and increasing its effectiveness is becoming one of the priority tasks. Therefore, researching the current state of the national environmental education and upbringing process and determining the scientific basis for solving problems should become the main goal of pedagogical research [4].

Based on these requirements, two interrelated trends in the development of environmental competence of students are noticeable: First, knowledge of objective ecological

relations is present in the quality of the means and result of the corresponding activity. Secondly, the organization and management of practical environmental relations is a direct process of this activity [3].

In the gradual and continuous organization of education in the field of nature protection, it is relatively common to rely on the system of family, pre-school education institutions, schools, educational institutions, labor teams. Based on the historical and logical principles of this scheme, there is no doubt that it will ensure the continuity of education. However, urgent environmental problems of today require a massive strengthening of this work at all levels. In order to increase the efficiency of nature protection work, it is of great importance to eliminate the deep-rooted indifference and "self-centeredness" mood in the minds of farm managers. After all, increasing the environmental responsibility of leaders and experts today by all means may bear fruit tomorrow. In this process, ecological education does not consist in the formation of theoretical views on nature, "at the same time, it also implies the formation of faith and practical training" [5]. After all, one of the main tasks of environmental education is to theoretically justify conflicts between nature and society in daily life activities, and to independently find practical solutions.

The formation of ecological practical activity skills in students and the development of nature protection into the meaning of life is an important feature of the socio-historical process. In this process, ethical, aesthetic and legal views turn into beliefs and responsibilities, and only if they are manifested in practical environmental activities, they become a criterion for the effectiveness of educational tools. Because the task of ecological education of social units is to create relatively stable, ideal forms of relations between nature and society.

In most pedagogical and didactic experiences, ecological education is revived and aimed at preserving nature. Although such an educational process has its own importance, it is a relatively low level. The higher, second stage represents the formation of practical skills of rational-constructive organization and management of nature protection activities in students, understanding the objective laws of nature and human relations.

Emotional and mental state plays an important role in the development of environmental competence in students. It is appropriate to divide the attitude towards ecological activities into positive-negative, optimistic-pessimistic and other opposing directions. Instead of understanding the positive or negative aspects of environmental responsibility, it is necessary to understand the positive-negative, optimistic-pessimistic aspects of the attitude to environmental responsibility. Because, in essence, environmental responsibility is a social phenomenon that does not have its antipode. The development of their exact criterion is methodologically important, as the absolutization of one or another side can increase conflicts in the internal structure of ecological activity and contradict its objective content. Therefore, as an important element of environmental responsibility, it is necessary to properly direct the education of the emotional and mental state and mood of students.

The issue of common environmental education is important in the development of environmental competence among students. It shows two relatively independent processes:

the possibility of a complex and systematic approach to environmental education arises from the need to harmonize different areas of education, to connect alternative directions based on a single goal.

it is necessary to maintain the historical and logical consistency of connections between different forms and levels of ecological education, and to ensure connections between their means and methods. In other words, the common character of these directions is manifested in their relationship to each other. In addition, on the basis of connecting education and upbringing with the interests of nature protection, a commonality emerges, and its features become a necessary condition for the development of ecological competence.

CONCLUSION. Until now, the conflicts between nature and society have become so intense that nature has taken revenge on man for his mistakes, humanity is forced to kneel before nature and repent. High forms of ecological ethical norms, new ethical criteria of attitude to nature are being formed. Purely universal ecological moral norms have risen to the level of politics, the moral content of ecological ideals has led to the wider coverage of other forms of social consciousness.

In conclusion, the environmental competence of students requires not only the formation of theoretical knowledge of nature protection, but also the development of practical relations in the relevant direction. The formation of practical ecological activities and becoming the content of lifestyle is not a simple task that can be realized by itself, spontaneously. One of the main tasks of ecological education is to theoretically justify conflicts between nature and society in daily life activities of students, and to guide them to independently find their practical solutions.

References:

1. Abdullaeva N.B. Modern problems of ecoethics - Tashkent: Science. 2019. -B. 7.
2. Ahmadaliev Yu.I. Ethnoecology. - Fergana: "Slassic", - 2021. -B. 79.
3. Ismailova G. Improving the methods of formation and development of environmental culture among students (in the example of the history of Uzbekistan). Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) Dissertation in Pedagogical Sciences. -Namangan.: NamDU. 2022. -B. 44.
4. Mirzaeva N. Methodology for improving the system of environmental competence development in students. Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) Dissertation in Pedagogical Sciences. - Chirchik.: ChDPU. 2021. -B. 47.
5. Хошимова И. Диалектика глобального, регионального и локального в экологии. Автореф. дисс. на соис. уч. ст. докт. филос. наук. – Ташкент.: 1992. - С. 36.

